

**PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES AND CHARACTERISTICS IN
DEVELOPING TOLERANCE THINKING OF FUTURE FOREIGN
LANGUAGE TEACHERS**

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Abstract: In the world's advanced scientific research institutes and international centers, many research works are being conducted on the use of innovative educational technologies of modern pedagogy, on the development of effective teaching methods. Special attention is paid to the development of tolerant thinking, creative approach to education and pedagogical mechanisms of formation of creative attitude in foreign language teaching. Because it is based on the fact that the quality and effectiveness of teaching foreign languages depends on a creative approach to the teaching process, cooperative pedagogy.

Key words: Tolerant thinking, creativity, innovation, innovative-creative, economic, social, cultural, humanitarian, international harmony, modern technologies, solidarity, tolerant, social activity.

Today, in world pedagogy, there is an increasing need to develop tolerance thinking and professional skills of future specialists, especially future foreign language teachers, on the basis of innovative technologies. For this, special emphasis is placed on the organization of innovative, creative and interesting lesson processes, interactive conversation, games and creative exercises in the nature of competition. Through this, it will be possible to improve the quality of teaching foreign languages, to improve the educational technologies that serve the effectiveness of education, and to develop the thinking of creative tolerance and creativity and innovation skills in future teachers.

Therefore, special attention is paid to the organization of foreign education on the basis of advanced foreign experience and thereby to increase the quality of education, to create an atmosphere of creativity and tolerant relations. That is why it is important to develop the mindset of tolerance in future foreign language teachers.

In the world's advanced scientific research institutes and international centers, many research works are being conducted on the use of innovative educational technologies of modern pedagogy, on the development of effective teaching methods. Special attention is paid to the development of tolerant thinking, creative approach to education and pedagogical mechanisms of

formation of creative attitude in foreign language teaching. Because it turns out that the quality and effectiveness of teaching foreign languages depends on a creative approach to the teaching process, cooperative pedagogy.

"Declaration of Principles of Tolerance" by the General Conference of UNESCO shows that tolerance has been selected as one of the most important universal values in the process of globalization [1]. The principle that "the world must be built on the basis of moral and intellectual unity of mankind" defined in the UNESCO Charter expresses the main content of the UN activity. The UN performs the task of maintaining international peace and security, equal rights and self-determination of peoples, solving international problems of economic, social, cultural and humanitarian content, and coordinating the actions of nations and states in achieving these goals»[2]. Another document regulating international relations, the "International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights" states that each state is responsible for ensuring a way of life in accordance with universal norms for its people. Therefore, every state legally guarantees the creation of a tolerant culture in society and international tolerance at the global level [3].

Although joining such agreements is voluntary in international law, the state considers creating an environment of tolerant relations with its people as one of its important tasks. Today, Uzbekistan has also joined about 100 international conventions, pacts, and agreements that contribute to the formation of global cultural tolerance and deepen international integration [4]. President Sh.Mirziyoev also expresses the estimation of inter-ethnic harmony as our main achievement in the years of independence. "Today, representatives of more than 130 nationalities and peoples live in peace in our country - if I say that it is one of the most important achievements we have achieved during the period of independence, I think you will all agree with this opinion.

The role of 138 national cultural centers operating in our country in ensuring international harmony is incomparable. It is from this point of view that in the future, the strengthening of inter-ethnic harmony and solidarity will remain one of the priorities of the state policy in Uzbekistan»[5]. In fact, experts from foreign countries have emphasized that there is a high possibility of a civil war in Uzbekistan in the first years of independence among the Central Asian countries. But as a result of the strong social policy in our country, international harmony, solidarity and tolerant social activities have been established. Since the day of independence in Uzbekistan, the formation of democratic principles, the rights of the nations living on the Uzbek land, the development of the

traditions and customs of each nation, and the development of the language and further strengthening of respect for them are being carried out [6].

After the 21st century, new forms of global problems began to appear before humanity. That's why tolerance is very important in today's world. We live in an age of economic globalization and further mobilization, rapid development of communications, integration and interdependence, large-scale migration and migration, urbanization, and a new transformation of social structures. Each region is different, so intolerance is a threat to all regions of the world. Such a threat cannot be hidden behind national borders, because it has a universal character»[7]. Therefore, it is necessary to educate members of society, especially young people, in the spirit of tolerance in order to prevent inter-ethnic conflicts from arising and turning into inter-state wars due to the intolerance and bigoted thinking of people in the society. In this regard, within the framework of this research, it will be effective to analyze and spread the skills of preparing teachers of specific subjects for international communication.

The peculiarities of the development of international tolerance in future foreign language teachers are based on the following: First, it is somewhat effective and convenient to prepare future foreign language teachers for interethnic communication based on the development of interethnic tolerance.

Secondly, a foreign language graduate should be able to demonstrate religious tolerance that develops on the basis of inter-ethnic tolerance. Thirdly, the formation of moral tolerance in inter-ethnic communication will develop moral tolerance in the future teachers of specific sciences and help students to develop moral qualities. Moral tolerance means accepting another moral view or norm as it is[8].

Due to the fact that the tolerance that a future foreign language teacher should acquire is connected with the socio-aesthetic existence, he is not only concerned with knowing the things that exist in a person, but also with the things that have value for the aesthetic education of the perfect generation that will be needed in the future.

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